

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1960	Marko Juvan	1980	1993			Slovenian Professor of Literary Theory	
1960	Галушкин Александр Юрьевич	1981	1997	2014		Russian historian of literature and literary critic	1960-2014
1960	Jan Hajič	1982	1994			Czech computational linguist	
1960	Francisco Moreno Fernández	1982	1984			Spanish dialectologist and sociolinguist	
1960	Jordi Redondo	1982	1985			Spanish Associate in Greek Literature and Language	
1960	Vladimir Plungian	1982	1987			Russian linguist, specialist in linguistic typology and theory of grammar, morphology, corpus linguistics, African studies, poetics	
1960	Scott MacEachern	1982	1991			Canadian professor of archaeology and anthropology	
1960	Richard Sproat	1983	1985			American Research Scientist at Google (Natural Language & Speech)	
1960	Dirk Delabastita	1983	1990		w	Belgian literary and translation scholar	
1960	Harm den Boer	1983	1992			Dutch Professor of Iberoromance Literature	
1960	Katarzyna Dziubalska-Kołaczyk	1983	1988		w	Polish linguist	
1960	Sultana Wahnón	1983	1987		w	Spanish essayist and literary critic	
1960	Juliette Blevins	1983	1985		w	American linguist (phonology, phonetics, historical linguistics, and typology)	
1960	Benoit Vermander	1983	1984			French Professor of Religious Science	
1960	Alexandra Jaffe	1984	1990	2018		American Professor of Linguistics and Anthropology	1960-2018
1960	Eduardo Chirinos	1984	1997	2016		Peruvian professor of literature at the University of Montana, and a poet	1960-2016
1960	Mercedes Arriaga Flórez	1984	1993		w	Spanish philologist, Full professor in Italian philology	
1960	Adeline Masquelier	1984	1993		w	American Professor of Anthropology	
1960	Susan Hirsch	1984	1990		w	American legal anthropologist whose work has specialized in the study of legal language	
1960	France Martineau	1985	1989		w	Canadian linguist	
1960	Dace Bula	1985	1998		w	Latvian folklorist (History and theory of folklore, studies folklore and nationalism, nostalgia, eco-narratives)	
1960	José A. Álvarez Amorós	1985	1987			Spanish Professor of English	
1960	Begoña Aretxaga	1985	1992	2002	w	Spanish Basque anthropologist	1960-2002

1960	Rainer Winter	1986	2000		Austrian Professor of Media and Cultural Theory
1960	Rose-Marie Dechaine	1986	1993	w	Canadian linguist
1960	Eric Hoekstra	1986	1991		Dutch linguist, translator, writer, poet, literary critic and columnist
1960	Massimo Cova	1986	2016		Italian professor of art (painter)
1960	Villalva Alina	1986	1995	w	Portuguese linguist
1960	Usha Goswami	1986	1987	w	British researcher and professor of Cognitive Developmental Neuroscience
1960	Kamber Kamberi	1986	2000		Albanian Professor of Albanian Literature
1960	Joyce Tyldesley	1986		w	British archaeologist and Egyptologist, academic, writer and broadcaster who specialises in the women of ancient Egypt
1960	Sarah Franklin	1986	1992	w	American anthropologist who has substantially contributed to the fields of feminism, gender studies, cultural studies and the social study of reproductive and genetic technology
1960	Shearer West	1986	1986	w	British-American art-historian, academic and university administrator
1960	Katharina Von Kellenbach	1986	1990	w	German Professor of Religious Studies
1960	Kersti Börjars	1987	1987	w	Finnish linguist
1960	Zoltán Dörnyei	1987	1989		Hungarian linguist (Psycholinguistics)
1960	Lois Denissa	1987	No	w	Indonesian lecturer at Faculty of Art and Design, Maranatha Christian University (artistic creativity, paintings, and visual culture)
1960	Don Kulick	1987	1990		Swedish professor of anthropology
1960	Janet Afary	1987	1991	w	Iranian the Mellichamp Professor of Religious Studies
1960	James W. Watts	1987	1990		American Professor of Religion
1960	Nino Dobarjginidze	1988	1988	w	Georgian Professor of linguistics
1960	Koichi Tateishi	1988	1991		Japanese linguist
1960	Meiling Cheng	1988	1993	w	Thai noted performance art critic and poet, Professor of Dramatic Arts and English
1960	Albert Piette	1988			Belgian-French anthropologist
1960	Sidnie White Crawford	1988	1988	2018 w	American Professor of Classics and Religious Studies
1960	Jeffrey Trumbower	1988			American Professor of Religious Studies
1960	James R. Davila	1988	1988		American Professor of Early Jewish Studies

1960	Willy Maley	1989	1990		British literary critic, editor, teacher and writer	
1960	Mette Hjort	1989	1989	w	Danish professor of visual studies	
1960	Raffaella Zanuttini	1989	1991	w	Italian linguist (focuses primarily on syntax and linguistic variation)	
1960	Anthony Corbeill	1989	1990		American professor of Classics	
1960	Michel Clasquin	1989	2000		Dutch-South African Professor of Religious Studies	
1960	Donna Teevan	1989	1994	w	American Associate Professor of Theology and Religious Studies	
1960	Adam Kilgarriff	1990	1992	2015	British corpus linguist, lexicographer and co-author of Sketch Engine	1960-2015
1960	Kathleen James-Chakraborty	1990	1990	w	Irish Professor of Art History and Architectural Historian	
1960	Charles Ogbulogo	1990	1995		Nigerian Professor of English Language	
1960	Thomas A. DuBois	1990	1990		American Folklorist, scholar of Sámi culture	
1960	Stephen Prothero	1990	1990		American Professor of Religion	
1960	Antoni Navarro Amorós	1991	No		Spanish Professor of languages, literature and the performing arts and dance	
1960	Ярмакеев Искандер Энгелевич	1991			Russian philologist and educator	
1960	Alexander Alexakis	1991	1992		Greek Professor of Byzantine Philology	
1960	Lois Ellen Frank	1991	2011	w	American Native adjunct professor at the Institute of American Indian Arts (Traditional Arts and Ecology, Ethnobotany of Foods and Plants of the Southwest, and Indigenous Concepts of Native American Foods)	
1960	Michael J. Kolb	1991	1991		American anthropologist	
1960	Robert Dassanowsky	1992	1992		Austrian-American academic, writer, film and cultural historian, and producer	
1960	Wen-chin Ouyang	1992	1992	w	Thai professor of Arabic literature and comparative literature	
1960	France Winddance Twine	1992	1994	w	American sociologist, documentary filmmaker, a visual artist and an enrolled citizen of the Muskogee Creek Nation of Oklahoma	
1960	Carol Stabile	1992	1992	w	American Professor of Women's, Gender, and Sexuality Studies	

1960	Frederic W. Gleach	1992	1992		American anthropologist who specializes in Native American peoples of Virginia	
1960	Kate Cooper	1992	1992	w	British Professor of Ancient History	
1960	Marc Bizer	1993	1993		American Professor of French Literature	
1960	Stephen Bax	1993	2004	2017	British linguist (Professor in Applied Linguistics)	1960-2017
1960	Raivo Kelomees	1993	1994		Estonian painter, critic and new media researcher	
1960	Sami Tchak	1993	1993		Togolese writer	
1960	Theodore B. Fernald	1993	1994		American linguist	
1960	David Price	1993	1993		American anthropologist	
1960	Fu-shih Lin	1994	1994		Tai Research Fellow of the Institute of History and Philology	
1960	Силантьев Игорь Витальевич	1995	1995		Russian literary critic, specialist in Russian literature and theory of literature	
1960	Elina Kahla	1995	2007	w	Finnish philologist	
1960	Christian van Gorder	1995	1995		American Associate Professor of Religion	
1960	Cathrine Degnen	1996	2003	w	British Professor of Social and Cultural Anthropology	
1960	Krasimira Fileva	1996	1996	w	Bulgarian Professor, Department of Piano and Accordion, Academy of Music, Dance and Fine Arts (Music, Musicology, and Psychology of Music)	
1960	Naser Nikoubakht	1996	1996		Iranian Professor of Persian language and Literature	
1960	Ni Made Suryati	1997	2012	w	Indonesian lecturer in linguistics of Faculty of Arts	
1960	Agus Nuryatin	1998	2008		Indonesian Professor of Indonesian Language and Literature	
1960	Georges Tamer	1998	2000		German the Chair of Oriental Philology and Islamic Studies	
1960	Angela Kluge	1999	2014	w	German linguist	
1960	Mirsad Kunić	2001	2007		Bosnian literature critic (oral literature, epic literature)	
1960	Sylvester Jussem	2004	No		Malaysian Asian Modern & Contemporary painter and educator of Faculty of Applied and Creative Arts	
1960	Hilman Pardede	2006	2011		Indonesian linguist of Universitas Nommensen	
1961	Peter J Hutchings	1981	1990		Australian Dean of the School of Humanities and Communication Arts (arts, cinema, critical legal studies, literature, and philosophy)	
1961	Cyrus Patell	1983	1991		American literary and cultural critic (World literature, US literature)	

1961	Carmen Rabell	1983	2000	w	American Professor of Comparative Literature	
1961	Augusto Soares da Silva	1983	1999		Portuguese Professor of Portuguese Linguistics	
1961	Jasna Capo	1983	1990	w	Croatian Titular Professor Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research	
1961	Elleke Boehmer	1984	1990	w	South African Professor of World Literature in English	
1961	Hannu Salmi	1985	1993		Finnish Professor of Cultural History	
1961	Alexander Vovin	1985	1987		Russian-American Directeur d'études, linguistique historique	
1961	Carol E. Genetti	1986	1990	w	American linguist (Tibeto-Burman languages and languages of the Himalayans)	
1961	Deborah Lynn Steinberg	1986	1992	w	British-based American academic (Professor of Gender, Culture and Media Studies)	1961-2017
1961	Urpo Nikanne	1986	1986		Finnish linguist	
1961	Agustin Santana Talavera	1986	1990		Spanish Professor Antropology of Tourism	
1961	Ivo Hajnal	1986	1990		Swiss-Austrian philologist and linguist, specialized in Indo-European studies and Mycenaean Greek	
1961	Susan Black	1986	1986	w	British Scottish forensic anthropologist, anatomist and academic	
1961	Louis-Leon Christians	1986			Belgian professor of law and religion at Université catholique de Louvain	
1961	Jack B. Martin	1987	1991		American Chancellor Professor of English and Linguistics	
1961	Marc L. Greenberg	1987	1990		American linguist (Slavic (historical) accentology and dialectology)	
1961	Vieri Samek-Lodovici	1987	1996	w	Italian linguist	
1961	Lucienne Peiry	1987	1996	w	Swiss specialist in Outsider Art ("Art Brut"), an exhibition curator, a lecturer	
1961	Столяр Марина	1987		w	Ukrainian Head of the Department of Philosophy and Cultural Studies	
1961	Jan Blommaert	1987	1989		Belgian sociolinguist and linguistic anthropologist	
1961	Henriette de Swart	1987	1991	w	Dutch Professor in French linguistics and semantics	
1961	Alessandro Pancheri	1987	1993		Italian full professor in Philology of Italian literature	
1961	Robert Barsky	1987	1992		Canadian Research Chair in Law, Narrative, and Border Crossing in the Department of Law and Legal Studies	

1961	Alexander Vladimirovich Vovin	1987	1987		Russian-American linguist and philologist
1961	Ruth Mace	1987	1987	w	British anthropologist, biologist, and academic
1961	Sharon Macdonald	1987	1987	w	British anthropologist and museologist
1961	Judith Littleton	1987	1993	w	New Zealand anthropology academic
1961	Joel Robbins	1987	1998		American Socio-Cultural anthropologist
1961	Alistair McFadyen	1987			British Senior Lecturer, School of Philosophy, Religion and the History of Science
1961	William Anthony Nericcio	1988	1989		Mexican Chicano literary theorist, cultural critic, American Literature scholar
1961	Sandro Nielsen	1988	1992		Danish metalexigrapher
1961	Maria Cristina Paganoni	1988	2003	w	Italian Associate Professor of English Language and Translation
1961	Jeannine Beeken	1988	1991	w	Dutch (Flemish) linguist (lexicography, syntax, Dutch language)
1961	David Galeano Olivera	1988	1991		Paraguayan linguist, anthropologist, philologist, translator, and educator.
1961	Richard Utz	1988	1990		German medievalist (Medievalism, Medieval Studies, History of English Studies)
1961	Stefan Heidemann	1988	1993		German Orientalist
1961	Teresa Webber	1988	1988	w	British palaeographer, medievalist, and academic
1961	Rosemary J. Coombe	1988	1992	w	Canadian anthropologist and lawyer, Professor in the Department of Anthropology
1961	Jan-Olav Henriksen	1988	1990		Norwegian Professor, Philosophy of Religion
1961	Jes Martens	1988			Norwegian associate professor of the Early Iron Age at the Museum of Cultural History
1961	Ewa Płonowska Ziarek	1989	1989	w	Polish-American the Julian Park Professor of Comparative Literature (feminist political theory, modernism, continental philosophy, ethics, and critical theory)
1961	Rahilya Geybullayeva	1989	1989	w	Azerbaijani Professor of Comparative Literature
1961	Richard Lansdown	1989	1992		British Professor of Modern English Literature and Culture
1961	Roger Sabin	1989			British Professor of Popular Culture (writer about COMICS and lecturer at Central St. Martins in London)

1961	Odile Heynders	1989	1991	w	Dutch Professor of Comparative Literature and Head of the Department of Culture Studies
1961	Richard Lansdown	1989	1989		Dutch Professor of Modern English Literature and Culture
1961	Gruette-meier, Ralf	1989	1994		German Professor of Dutch literature
1961	Andre Indrawan	1989	2010		Indonesian Associate Professor of Music, Music Department
1961	Vladimir Tumanov	1989	1993		Ukrainian-Canadian Professor of Comparative Literature and Modern Languages
1961	Andrey Korotayev	1989	1993		Russian anthropologist, economic historian, comparative political scientist, demographer and sociologist
1961	Angelika Meirhofer	1989	1989	w	German Above-Doc Assistentin og Religion Studies
1961	Matthew Biro	1990	1994		American Professor of Modern and Contemporary Art
1961	Mariachiara Russo	1990	2002	w	Italian linguist (Full Professor of Spanish Language and Interpretation)
1961	Shuhrat Sirojiddinov	1990	1996		Uzbek rector, Alisher Navo'i Tashkent State University of the Uzbek Language and Literature
1961	Charlene Polio	1990	1992	w	American linguist
1961	Anđelko Mrkonjić	1990			Croatian art historian
1961	Yohannes Haile-Selassie	1990	2001		Ethiopian paleoanthropologist
1961	Martin Hose	1990	1990		German classical philologist
1961	Jan-Olav Henriksen	1990	1990		Norwegian Professor of Systematic Theology
1961	Kathryn Remlinger	1991	1995	w	American Professor of English (Linguisticsm sociolinguistics)
1961	Venetia Apostolidou	1991	1991	w	Greek Professor of Modern Greek Literature and Literary Education
1961	Henriëtte de Swart	1991	1991	w	Dutch linguist
1961	Leyla Neyzi	1991	1991	w	Turkish academic (anthropologist/sociologist/historian)
1961	Vasilios N. Makrides	1991	1991		Greek orthodox theologian and religious scholar
1961	Wouter Hanegraaff	1991	1995		Dutch full professor of History of Hermetic Philosophy
1961	Mohamad Jafre Zainol Abidin	1992	1992		Malaysian associate Professor in TESOL and English
1961	Zilibele Mtumane	1992	1999		South African Associate Professor of African Languages

1961	Shobhana Lakshmi	1992	1992	w	American linguist (Tibeto-Burman languages and language documentation)	
1961	Bernard Bate	1992	2000	2016	American linguistic anthropologist (Tamil language and the history of public speaking)	1960-2016
1961	Sarah Green	1992	1992	w	British Professor of social and cultural anthropology	
1961	Roland Kadan	1992	1994		Austrian Theological Lecturer	
1961	Susan Cahan	1993	2003	w	American art historian, curator and educator (contemporary art and the history of museums)	
1961	Roger Leong	1993	No		Australian Senior Curator, Museum of Applied Arts and Sciences (fashion)	
1961	Juan Fernando Sellés Dauder	1993	1994		Spanish Professor of Philosophical Antropology	
1961	Vijaya R Nagarajan	1993		w	Indian-American Associate Professor, Theology/Religious Studies & Environmental Studies	
1961	Dirk Büchner	1993			German Professor Religious Studies	
1961	Saba Mahmood	1994	1998	2018	Pakistani anthropology and political theory	1961-2018
1961	Tony Collins	1995	1996		British sports and social historian and author specialising in Northern England and rugby football	
1961	Albena Bakratcheva	1995	1995	w	Bulgarian Professor of American Literature	
1961	Nóra Séllei	1995	1996	w	Hungarian researcher of Doctoral School of Literary and Cultural Studies	
1961	Helen Tan	1995	2011	w	Malaysian senior lecturer of Faculty of Modern Language and Communication	
1961	Christopher Partridge	1995			British Professor of Religious Studies	
1961	Jeff MacSwan	1996	1998		American linguist and educational researcher	
1961	David Graeber	1996	1996		American anthropologist, anarchist activist	
1961	Richard Foltz	1996	1996		American-Canadian specialist in the history of Iranian civilization—what is sometimes referred to as "Greater Iran"	
1961	Mark R. V. Southern	1997	1997	2006	German Indo-Europeanist and professor of German and linguistics	1961-2006
1961	Maria Gough	1997	1997	w	Australian art historian	
1961	Susan Hogan	1997		w	British Professor in Cultural Studies & Art Therapy at the University of Derby	

1961	Frano Dulibić	1998	2002		Croatian Art historian (Croatian painting and sculpture of the first half of the 20th century, history of graphic cartoons, caricatures, illustrations, and cartoon strips and participates in science projects and symposiums)
1961	Huda Hadi Khalil	2000	No	w	Iraqi Asst. Prof. of English Language and Linguistics
1961	Peter Vuust	2000	2006		Danish Professor of Music (cognitive neuroscience of music, predictive coding, music analysis, music theory, eudaimonia)
1961	Omid Tabibzadeh	2000	2000		Iranian linguist
1961	Adolfo Cifuentes	2000	2010		Colombian Professor of Photography
1961	Silke Fischer	2001	2004	w	German linguist
1961	Deborah Padfield	2002	2013	w	British visual artist (lens based media and interdisciplinary practice and research within Fine Art and Medicine)
1961	Caroline Rannersberger	2006	2010	w	Australian painter and printmaker
1961	Marian Tutui	2007	2007		Romanian researcher in cinema, film critic
1961	Nicoletta Gatti	2007		w	Italian Fellow of Dept. for the Study of Religions
1961	Hassan El-Nabih	2009	2010		Palestinean linguist
1962	Hilary du Cros	1983	1996	w	Australian archaeologist and cultural tourism teacher
1962	Carole Cusack	1984	1996	w	Australian Professor of Religious Studies
1962	Mercy Adesanya-Davies	1985	2003	w	Nigerian Associate Professor of Applied Linguistics and Education
1962	Carles Feixa	1985	1990		Spanish professor of social anthropology
1962	Martin Haase	1985	1991		German linguist, polyglot, and podcaster
1962	Lada Badurina	1985	1985	w	Croatian linguist
1962	Nélio Tanios Porto	1985	2002		Brazilian Professor de Música (Piano e Composição Musical)
1962	Joerg Ruepke	1985	1989		German scholar of comparative religion and classical philology
1962	Lisa LS Cheng	1986	1991	w	Chinese linguist (syntax-semantics interface, syntax-prosody interface, syntax-processing interface, Chinese languages, Bantu languages)
1962	Nikola Petković	1986	1996		Croatian professor of comparative literature
1962	Virginia Yip	1986	1989	w	Hong Kong linguist and writer

1962	Kamila Ghazali	1986	1999	w	Malaysian Professor of Linguistics and Associate Vice-Chancellor (International) at the University of Malaya	
1962	Itziar Laka	1986	1990	w	Spanish Full Professor Dept. of Linguistics and Basque Studies	
1962	Karen Ramey Burns	1986	1987	2012 w	American forensic anthropologist known for work in international human rights	1962-2012
1962	Jeffrey H. Cohen	1986	1994		American anthropologist	
1962	Steven Rubenstein	1986	1995	2012	American anthropologist	1962-2012
1962	Katy Deepwell	1987	1991	w	British feminist art critic and academic	
1962	Xander Van Eck	1987	1994		Dutch Professor of Art History	
1962	Anne Abeillé	1987	1991	w	French linguist	
1962	Andrea Moro	1987	1987		Italian linguist and neuroscientist	
1962	Thomas Hylland Eriksen	1987	1991		Norwegian social anthropologist	
1962	Joakim Nivre	1987	1992		Swedish Professor of Computational Linguistics	
1962	Enric Vallduví	1987	1990		Spanish linguist	
1962	Nikolai Grube	1987	1990		German epigrapher	
1962	Nikolay Kradin	1987	1990		Russian anthropologist and archaeologist	
1962	Dan Jurafsky	1988	1992		American Professor of Linguistics and Computer Science	
1962	Arne Eigenfeldt	1988	1993		Canadian composer and creator of interactive and generative music systems	
1962	Eric Castelli	1988	1989		French linguist	
1962	Salvatore Attardo	1988	1991		Italian full professor at Texas A&M University–Commerce and the editor-in-chief of Humor	
1962	Nina Kudiš	1988	1998	w	Slovenian Professor of Art History (painting)	
1962	Sofia Kotzabassi	1988	1988	w	Greek Professor of Byzantine Philology (Byzantine Philology, Greek Paleography, Byzantine Literature)	
1962	Monica Esposito	1988	1993	2011 w	Italian one of the world's foremost scholars of Chinese religion specializing in the history, texts, and practices of Daoism (15th to 20th centuries)	1962-2011
1962	Christoph K. Neumann	1988	1992		German Orientalist with a focus on Turkology	
1962	Alison Louise Spedding	1988	1989	w	British anthropologist and fantasy author	
1962	Osman Gashi	1989	1989		Albanian Professor of World and Comparative Literature	

1962	Jörg Rüpke	1989	1989		German scholar of comparative religion and classical philology
1962	Dawn Atkins	1989		1999 w	American anthropologist, second-generation feminist and writer (journalism, anthropology, body image, science fiction and fantasy, feminism, gender and sexuality studies, and Neopaganism)
1962	Karin Willemse	1989		w	Dutch Assistant Professor of History of Africa, and of Gender and Islam
1962	Mahmoud El-Khadragy	1990	1996		Egyptian Professor of Egyptology
1962	Gerardine Meaney	1990	1990	w	Irish Professor of Cultural Theory (gender, ethnic and national identities in literature and culture and the application of new digital methodologies to humanities research)
1962	Sharon Armon-Lotem	1990	1997	w	Israeli Associate Professor in the Department of English Literature and Linguistics
1962	Glecy Cruz Atienza	1990	2001	w	Philippino Professor of Philippine Literature and Theater
1962	Tvrtko Zebec	1990	2005		Croatian senior researcher, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research (dance research, ethnology, ethnochoreology, intangible cultural heritage, anthropology of dance)
1962	Rei Terada	1990	1990	w	American Professor of Comparative Literature
1962	Bedia Demiriş	1990	1990		Turkish Professor of Latin language and Literature
1962	Kira Hall	1990	1995	w	American Professor of Linguistics and Anthropology
1962	Juliet E. Morrow	1990	1996	w	American archaeologist and a professor of Anthropology
1962	Manel Olle	1990	1999		Spanish Professor of Chinese Modern and Contemporary Culture and History
1962	Devin J. Stewart	1990	1990		American professor of Islamic studies and Arabic language and literature
1962	Franz Pöchhacker	1991	1993		Austrian translation studies
1962	Jaś Elsner	1991	1991		British art historian and classicist
1962	Gijs Mulder	1991	1998		Dutch assistant professor of Spanish language and culture
1962	Kersti Markus	1991	2000	w	Estonian Professor of Art History

1962	Andreas Külzer	1991	1993		German Byzantine and historical geographer	
1962	Klaus von Heusinger	1991	1992		German Professor für Germanistische Linguistik	
1962	Susanne Maria Michaelis	1991	1991	w	German specialist in creole linguistics	
1962	Isabel Muguruza Roca	1991	1995	w	Spanish Professor of Spanish Literature	
1962	Ekaterina Anastasova	1991	1996	w	Bulgarian Head of Balkan Ethnology Department (Ethnology, Social Anthropology, Ethnolinguistics)	
1962	Curtis Rice	1991	1991		Norwegian American-born linguist and the rector of Oslo Metropolitan University	
1962	Srinivas Aravamudan	1991		2016	American Professor of English, Literature, and Romance Studies	1962-2016
1962	Dia Cha	1991	2000	w	American Associate Professor of Anthropology and Ethnic Studies	
1962	Caxton Nyahela	1991	2013		Kenyan Lecturer of Religious Studies	
1962	Jan Čermák	1992			Czech linguist, medievalist and translator from English and Finnish	
1962	Ingo Plag	1992	1993		German Professor of English Linguistics	
1962	Algis Uždavinys	1992	2000	2010	Lithuanian philosopher and scholar	1962-2010
1962	Guido Bonsaver	1992			Italian Professor of Italian Cultural History	
1962	Peter Lunenfeld	1993	1994		American critic and theorist of digital media	
1962	Ralf van Bühren	1993	2006		German art historian, theologian, and Church historian	
1962	Amiri Swaleh	1993	2011		Kenyan doctor of Kiswahili Literature and Sociolinguistics	
1962	Lukasz Guzek	1993	2005		Polish scientific researcher in art history with art criticism and curatorial practice	
1962	Manel Ollé	1993	1999		Spanish Professor of Chinese Modern and Contemporary Culture and History	
1962	César Salgado	1993	1993		American Associate Professor in the Department of Spanish and Portuguese	
1962	Volkhard Krech	1993	1995		German Professor of science of religion	
1962	Etim E Okon	1993	1999		Nigerian Associate Professor, Department of Religious and Cultural Studies	
1962	Nada Shabout	1994	1999	w	American art historian (modern Iraqi art)	
1962	Imelda Udoh	1994	1998	w	Nigerian Professor of Linguistics and Nigeria Languages	
1962	Simona Modreanu	1994	1997	w	Romanian Professor of French literature	

1962	Manisha Sinha	1994	1994	w	Indian-American historian, and the Draper Chair in American History
1962	Hristo Kyuchukov	1994	1995		Bulgarian-German Muslim Rom (leading specialist in the field of Romani language and education of Roma children in Europe)
1962	Nikki Sullivan	1995	2001	w	Australian Associate Professor of Cultural Studies
1962	Bistra Andreeva	1995	2005	w	German Professor of Phonetics and Phonology
1962	Randall Halle	1995	1995		German the Klaus W. Jonas Professor of German Film and Cultural Studies
1962	Mihaela Secrieru	1995	1998	w	Romanian Professor of Romanian Language
1962	Martin Rothgangel	1995			Austrian Professor of Religion
1962	Geir Afdal	1995	2005		Norwegian Professor of Religious Education at MF Norwegian School of Theology
1962	Malachy Okwueze	1995			Nigerian professor of Religion
1962	Jeffrey J. Kripal	1995			American the J. Newton Rayzor Chair in Philosophy and Religious Thought
1962	Chris Andrews	1995			Australian translator and writer
1962	Halleh Ghorashi	1996	2001	w	Iranian-Dutch anthropologist
1962	Nadia Abu El Haj	1996	2001	w	American professor of anthropology
1962	Miyako Inoue	1996	1996	w	American associate professor in the Department of Cultural and Social Anthropology
1962	Erik Mueggler	1996	1996		American anthropologist
1962	Eliza Richards	1997	1997	w	American associate professor of Dept of English and Comparative Literature
1962	DA Premakumara de Silva	1997	2005		Sri Lankian Senior Professor of Sociology (anthropology and sociology)
1962	Nenad Veličković	1998	2010		Bosnian writer and playwright
1962	Heather Levi	1998	2001	w	American anthropologist best known for her research in lucha libre
1962	Wan Roselezam Wan Yahya	1999	1999	w	Malaysian associate professor in English literature
1962	Jelani BHarun	1999	1999		Malaysian Professor of Malay Literature
1962	Julie Andreyev	1999	2019	w	Canadian multidisciplinary artist
1962	Sarah F. Maclaren	1999	1999	w	British Anglo-Italian cultural theorist, sociologist and anthropologist

1962	Bettina Hauge	2000	2008	w	Danish anthropologist whose work is concerned with the social implications of natural phenomena such as wind, water and above all light
1962	Ezichi Ituma	2000	2006		Nigerian Associate Professor at Department of Religion and Cultural Studies
1962	Anthony B. C. Chiegboka	2001			Nigerian Professor of Religion and Society
1962	Natalia Surguladze	2003	2005	w	Georgian head of the Department of European Studies (Phraseology, Paremiology, Semiotics, lingvoculturology)
1962	Asare-Danso, Seth	2005	2011		Ghanaian Associate Professor of Religious and Moral Education
1962	Christopher Braddock	2008	2008		New Zealand artist (painter) and writer, and Professor of Visual Arts
1962	Patrick Pound	2008	2011		New Zealand Associate Professor, Arts and Performance, painter (photography)
1962	Ilco Jovanov	2009			North Macedonian Professor of Music Art
1962	Fiona Coffey	2011	2013	w	Irish Associate Director, Wesleyan University Center for the Arts
1963	Sheng-Ching Chang	1984	2002	w	Taiwanese art historian
1963	Andrea Cornwall	1985	1996	w	British Professor of Global Development & Anthropology
1963	Lorenza Mondada	1985	1994	w	Swiss linguist
1963	Galia Sabar	1985	1993	w	Israeli Professor of African Studies
1963	Pascal Lefèvre	1986	2003		Belgian comics historian and theorist
1963	Irwan Abdullah	1986	1994		Indonesian Professor of Anthropology
1963	Richard Finn	1986	2006		British Priest, Academic, Theologian, Historian
1963	Ortwin de Graef	1987	1990		Belgian Full Professor at the Faculty of Arts (ethics, history and determinism in the Post-Romantic condition)
1963	Stephen Campbell	1987	1993		Irish art historian (Italian art from the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries)
1963	Angel Esteban	1987	1990		Spanish professor of Latin American literature
1963	Martin Haspelmath	1987	1993		German linguist (typology, language change, language contact, Lezgian language)

1963 Andrej Kibrik	1987	1988		Russian linguist (cognitive linguistics, discourse analysis, semantics, grammar, functional linguistics, linguistic typology, areal linguistics, language documentation.)
1963 Sharon Inkelas	1987	1989	w	American Professor and former Chair of the Linguistics Department
1963 Adele Goldberg	1989	1992	w	American linguist
1963 Stephen Matthews	1989	1991		American linguist
1963 Yaron Matras	1989			British linguist
1963 Norbert Corver	1989	1990		Dutch professor of Dutch Linguistics
1963 Javier Velaza	1989	1990		Spanish classical philologist, poet and Spanish writer
1963 Anna T. Litovkina	1989	1994	w	Hungarian linguist, psychologist and a coach
1963 Julia Crick	1989		w	British Professor of Palaeography and Manuscript Studies
1963 Robert Warrior	1990	1999		American Osage scholar and the Hall Distinguished Professor of American Literature and Culture
1963 Katharine Cockin	1990	1994	w	British Professor of Department of Literature Film and Theatre Studies
1963 Steve Reinke	1990	No		Canadian video artist and filmmaker
1963 Michael Everson	1990	No		American-Irish linguist, script encoder, typesetter, font designer, and publisher
1963 Shishir Bhattacharja	1990	2007		Bangladeshi linguist, writer, columnist, and a professor of the French language
1963 Timothy Beal	1990	1991		American the Florence Harkness Professor of Religion
1963 Antonius Liedhegener	1990	1996		German modern historian
1963 Yvette Watt	1991	2009	w	Australian Lecturer, Tasmanian College of the Arts
1963 Peter Schrijver	1991	1991		Dutch linguist and a professor of Celtic languages
1963 Michael W. Kwakkelstein	1991	1994		Dutch Professor of Art History (visual arts of the Renaissance in Italy and the Low Countries)
1963 Dick Houtman	1991	1994		Dutch Professor of Sociology of Culture and Religion
1963 Rajko Muršič	1991	1998		Slovenian professor of cultural anthropology (ethnologist)
1963 Johan Schimanski	1991	1997		Swedish Prof. of Comparative Literature
1963 Reina Lewis	1992	1994	w	British art historian
1963 Marko Tadić	1992	1994		Croatian linguist

1963	Prof.dr. Magda Ahmed Mohamed Abdalla	1992	2000	w	Egyptian Associate Professor of Ancient History in Faculty of Arts
1963	Hassan AH Gadalla	1992	1999		Egyptian Professor of Linguistics and Translation, Dept. of English
1963	Mara Grudule ; Māra Grudule	1992	1995	w	Latvian Researcher, Institute of Literature, Folklore and Arts
1963	Nor Faridah Abdul Manaf	1992	2003	w	Malaysian Professor of English Language and Literature
1963	Julie Cupples	1992	2002	w	American Professor of Human Geography and Cultural Studies
1963	Hans-Jörg Schmid	1992	1992		German linguist
1963	Alessandro Bausi	1992	1992		Italian philologist (Ethiopic texts and manuscripts)
1963	Katarzyna Jaszczolt	1992	1999	w	Polish-British linguist and philosopher
1963	Rakhshanda Jalil	1992		w	Indian writer, critic and literary historian
1963	Kate Tilleczek	1993	2003	w	Canadian full professor of Child/Youth Cultures and Transitions
1963	Anja Nikolic-Hoyt	1993	2001	w	Croatian Scientific associate at Linguistic Research Institute (lexicography)
1963	Yuliana Setyaningsih	1993	2008	w	Indonesian Senior Lecturer in Phonology and Language Teaching and Learning
1963	Zvi Mark	1993	2001		Israeli researcher, Professor of Literature of the Jewish People
1963	Adil Çiftçi	1993	1998		Turkish Professor of Sociology of Religion
1963	Emma Dench	1993	1993	w	British English ancient historian, classicist, and academic administrator
1963	Jeffrey Klenotic	1994	1996		American Associate Professor of Communication Arts
1963	Aida Audeh	1995	2002	w	American Administrative Division Head, Fine Arts (the painting and sculpture of 18th-19th centuries in Europe, in art theory, and the history of academies during the Baroque period in Europe)
1963	Xenofon Bitsikas	1995	2000		Greek artist, Professor (Painting) and Dean of the School of Fine Arts
1963	Tamar Wolf-Monzon	1995	1995	w	Israeli Professor of Hebrew Literature
1963	Matjaž Birk	1995	1997		Slovenian linguist

1963	José María Pérez Fernández	1995	1995		Spanish profesor titular of English Literature and Cultural Translation
1963	Metin Ekici	1995	1996		Turkish researcher in Folklor Theories and Turkish Folk Literature
1963	Janika Oras	1995	2008	w	Estonian senior researcher, Estonian Folklore Archives (Folklore, Ethnomusicology, Cultural Studies)
1963	Aneta Pavlenko	1995	1997	w	Ukrainian-American linguist
1963	Peter Gottschalk	1995	1995		British Professor of Religion
1963	Cosoveanu Gabriel	1996	1996		Romanian Professor of Romanian Literature
1963	Predrag Cveticanin	1996	2011		Serbian professor of Art
1963	Любовь Арбачакова	1996	1998	w	Russian writer, painter and folklorist (шорский живописец и график, поэт, ученый-исследователь шорского героического эпоса)
1963	Assoc. Prof. Jalaini Abu Hassan	1996	2011		Malaysian painter
1963	Margaret Bender	1996	1996	w	American anthropologist who specializes in the language and culture of the Cherokee people
1963	Elpida Rikou	1997	1997	w	Greek sociologist, anthropologist, social psychologist and art historian in Athens
1963	David Ehrenpreis	1998	1998		American Professor of Art History, co-founder of the Institute for Visual Studies
1963	Faramarz Mirzaei	1998	1998		Iranian Professor of Arabic Language and Literature
1963	Patricia Dold	1998	2005	w	Canadian Associate Professor of Religious Studies
1963	Sandeep Bhagwati	1999	No		German composer of western classical music and an academic teacher
1963	Ramon Parramon Arimany	2000	2015		Spanish Project manager in the cultural field, visual artist, curator and professor
1963	Jessie Little Doe Baird	2000	2017	w	American linguist (Wampanoag language)
1963	Matei Bejenaru	2001	2006		Romanian Professor of Photography and Video, visual artist (painter)
1963	Sonja Cvetković	2001	2010	w	Serbian Associate professor, Faculty of Arts (musicology)
1963	Ayobami Kehinde	2002	2002		Nigerian Professor of African, Comparative and Postcolonial Literatures
1963	Iguanre Solomon	2003	2005		Nigerian Associate Professor of Dramatic Literature

1963 Prof. Saraswati Vidyarthi	2003	2007	w	Indian (Carnatic) vocalist and composer
1963 Andy Best-Dunkley	2005	No		British media artist and sculptor (specialising in playful and provocative interactions in physical spaces such as galleries and museums, in the public city space, as well as in the online virtual realm of cyberspace)
1963 Elizabeth Grant	2007	2007	w	Australian architectural anthropologist, criminologist and academic working in the field of Indigenous Architecture
1963 Pauline Dimech	2008	2015	w	Maltese Lecturer in Systematic Theology, and Religious Educator
1963 Dr Neil March	2014	2014		British Composer and Recording Artist
1964 Ricardo Ventura Santos	1984	1991		Brazilian anthropologist
1964 April McMahon	1985	1989	w	British linguist
1964 Janet Bennion	1985	1996	w	American Professor of Anthropology (gender dynamics in Mormon fundamentalist communities which practice polygamy)
1964 Ann Pellegrini	1985	1994	w	American Professor of Performance Studies (Tisch School of the Arts) and Social and Cultural Analysis
1964 Linda Woodhead	1985	2009	w	British Professor of Sociology of Religion
1964 Marjo de Theije	1986	1999	w	Dutch associate professor Social and Cultural Anthropology
1964 Linda Woodhead	1986	No	w	British academic specialising in the religious studies and sociology of religion
1964 Marc Michael Epstein	1986	1992		American Professor of Religion and Visual Culture
1964 Laura A. Michaelis	1987	1993	w	American Professor of Linguistics
1964 Bart Eeckhout	1987	1998		Belgian Professor of English and American Literature
1964 Guido Vanden Wyngaerd	1987	1990		Dutch linguist
1964 John Gee	1987	1998		American professional Egyptologist
1964 Carl Veters	1988	1992		French linguist
1964 Gereon Müller	1988	1996		German linguist
1964 Andreas C. Lehmann	1988	1992		German Professor of Musicology (musicology, music psychology)
1964 Tony McEneaney	1989	1995		British the Distinguished Professor of English Language and Linguistics
1964 Ianthi Tsimpli	1989	1992	w	Greek linguist

1964	Nevena Dakovic	1989	1992	w	Serbian Professor of Film and Media Studies	
1964	Robbie B. H. Goh	1989	1993		Singaporean Professor of Literature	
1964	Paul Innes	1990	1991		British Professor of Shakespeare Studies & Academic Subject Leader in Literary and Critical Studies	
1964	Harvey Whitehouse	1990	1990		British social anthropologist	
1964	Mette Sandbye	1990	1999	w	Danish professor and head of department at the Department of Arts and Cultural Sciences, art reviewer	
1964	Radhika Viruru	1990	1998	w	Indian Teaching Learning & Culture	
1964	Ran HaCohen	1990	2002		Israeli scholar, university teacher, and translator	
1964	Jonathan Ginzburg	1990	1992		Israeli-British linguist	
1964	Janet Roitman	1990	1996	w	American anthropologist	
1964	Ulrike Garde	1991	2007	w	Australian Senior Lecturer in German Studies	
1964	Tista Bagchi	1991	1993	w	Indian linguist and ethicist	
1964	Margaret Kelleher	1991	1991	w	Irish Full professor and chair of Anglo-Irish Literature and Drama	
1964	Nee Olufajo	1991	1995		Nigerian Professor in Linguistics and African Languages	
1964	Søren Wichmann	1991	1996		Norwegian historical linguistics, linguistic typology, Mesoamerican languages, and epigraphy	
1964	Snježana Kordić	1991	1993	w	Croatian linguist (Serbo-Croatian language, syntax, sociolinguistics)	
1964	David Silva	1991	1992		American linguist and university administrator	
1964	Dounia Bouzar	1991	No	2016 w	French anthropologist, writer and educator (better acceptance of Muslims, especially Muslim women, in France)	
1964	Tobias Hecht	1991	1995		American anthropologist, ethnographer, and translator	
1964	Frank Guenther	1992	1993		American computational and cognitive neuroscientist	
1964	Ad Neeleman	1992	1994		Dutch linguist	
1964	Ene Vainik	1992	1995		Estonian Senior research fellow at the Institute of the Estonian Language	
1964	Dr Farida Yasmeen Panhwar	1992	2017	w	Pakistani associate Professor of Institute of English Language and Literature	
1964	Dominic Montserrat	1992		2004	British egyptologist and papyrologist	1964-2004
1964	Rebecca E. Biron	1993	1993	w	American professor of Spanish and comparative literature	

1964	Hannah Higgins	1993	1994	w	American writer and academic	
1964	Charles Reiss	1993	1995		American linguist (phonology, historical linguistics, and cognitive science)	
1964	Ana Mariella Bacigalupo	1993	1994	w	Peruvian anthropologist	
1964	Jeanette Erazo Heufelder	1993	1993	w	German ethnologist	
1964	Jasmina Mojsieva Guseva	1994	1994	w	North Macedonian researcher in Balkan literature and culture	
1964	Nadja Zgonik	1994	1997	w	Slovenian art historian (art of modernism, postmodernism and of the contemporary period)	
1964	Jila Ghomeshi	1994	1996	w	Iranian-Canadian linguist	
1964	Alexander Argüelles	1994	1994		American linguist	
1964	Daphne Berdahl	1994	1995	2007 w	German anthropologist (gender and consumption as well as her writing on post-communist nostalgia has been widely cited by scholars of post-socialism)	1964-2007
1964	Sabine Hyland	1994	1994	w	American anthropologist and ethnohistorian working in the Andes, Professor of World Christianity	
1964	Scott Sandage	1994	1995		American cultural historian at Carnegie Mellon University	
1964	Ken Gonzales-Day	1995	1995		American artist, Professor of Art (photo-based conceptual projects exploring identity and the construction of race)	
1964	Charles Laughlin	1995	1996		American Professor of Chinese Literature	
1964	Morten Søndergaard	1995	2006		Danish writer, translator, editor and artist	
1964	Nijazi Ramadani	1995	No		Albanian poet, novelist, social critic, art critic, literary critic political analyst and intellectual	
1964	Gonda Van Steen	1995	1995	w	Belgian-American classical scholar and linguist, who specialises in ancient and modern Greek language and literature	
1964	Lorenzo Perilli	1996			Italian classicist and academic	
1964	Musa Dube	1996	1997	w	Botswana feminist theologian (postcolonial biblical scholarship)	
1964	Adam L. Kern	1997	1997		American Professor of Japanese Literature and Visual Culture	
1964	Farzad Sharifian	1997	2003		Australian linguist (pioneer of Cultural Linguistics)	

1964	Alberto de Campo	1997	2009		Austrian electronic musician, composer, researcher and software designer	
1964	Dr. Kavita Singh	1997	1997	w	Indian Professor of art history and currently serves as the Dean at the School of Arts and Aesthetics	
1964	Héctor Jaimes	1997	1998		Venezuelan Professor of Latin American Literature and Culture	
1964	Besim Muhadri	1997	2011		Albanian professor of Literature and Language	
1964	Anne E. Monius	1997	1997	2019 w	American Indologist and religious scholar	1964-2019
1964	Dawn Prince-Hughes	1997	1997	w	American anthropologist, primatologist, and ethologist	
1964	Oriare Nyarwath	1997	2009		Kenyan Lecturer of Philosophy and Religious Studies	
1964	Maria Mavroudi	1998	1998	w	Greek Professor of History and Classics (classical Greek and Arabic, Coptic, Latin, and Syriac, and speaks modern Greek and English)	
1964	Audrius Beinorius	1998	1998		Lithuanian philosopher, orientalist (specialist of Indology, Buddhist studies and Comparative Studies), translator, Habilitated Doctor of Humane Letters	
1964	Mary L. Keller	1998	2002	w	American Lecturer, Religious Studies	
1964	Sturla Stålsett	1998	1998		Norwegian professor of diakonia, religion and society	
1964	Suchandra Ghosh	1998	1998	w	Indian Professor, Ancient Indian History & Culture	
1964	Tahera Qutbuddin	1999	1999	w	Egyptian scholar of classical Arabic literature and Islamic studies	
1964	Babasehinde A Ademuleya	1999	2002		Nigerian sculptor and African art historian	
1964	Bahar Davary	1999		w	American Associate professor of Theology and Religious Studies	
1964	William N. Fenton	2000	2003		American anthropologist and lawyer, an Assistant Professor of Anthropology	
1964	Erica Appellos	2000	2000	w	Swedish associate professor in Philosophy of Religion	
1964	Hope Yu	2001	2007	w	Philippino short story writer/poet	
1964	Tony D. Sampson	2002	2009		British critical theorist (philosophies of media technology, design thinking, social and immersive user experiences and neurocultures)	
1964	Alireza Bonyadi	2003	2011		Iranian linguist	
1964	Azad Tahir Salih Hamawandy	2004	2004		Iragi Kurdish Instructor (Lecturer) of English Department	

1964 Giuliano Chiapparini
1964 Kenneth Owen Smith
1964 Aurora Faye Martinez

2004
2005 2005
2016 No

w

Italian Researcher of History of Religion
American Associate Professor of Music
American Doctoral researcher (Manuscripts, Early
Modern Literature, Romanticism Pastoral and Genre)